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From Amazon: Lessons for the Asian Church

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The Synod of Bishops for the Pan-Amazon region met in Rome from 6 to 27 October 2019. The minor controversies overshadowing it threatens to overshadow its major contribution to the universal Church. It was found very positive response from diverse places. Further, it has important implications for the Church in Asia.

San Diego Bishop Robert McElroy, urged the Church in America to embrace the type of synodal pathway that the church in the Amazon has been undergoing. McElroy was chosen by Pope Francis to attend the Amazon synod, a gathering that the U.S. bishop found marked by "deep and broad consultation, the willingness to accept arduous choices, the search for renewal and reform at every level, and unswerving faith in the constancy of God's presence in the community." Reports National Catholic Reporter

Bishop Franz-Josef Bode of Osnabrück, Germany, told the National Catholic Register that the recent synod's push for married priests and women deacons 'complies with our reflections' for the German Church's upcoming 'Synodal Path.'

Besides accepting the “synodal path,” we in India have a lot to learn from it, leading to an ecological conversion respecting the earth and the indigenous mentality.

Becoming Subjects of One’s Own History

Regarding its proposal to adopt an “Amazonian rite” Cardinal Beniamino Stella, Prefect of the Congregation for the Clergy, said it was natural for people to want to communicate through their “local language and symbols, colours, and stories”.

He recalled how the bishops of the Amazon Region are dealing with “diversified realities” that are multi-ethnic and multi-linguistic. Any rite expresses the history and the spirituality of a people, he said.

Fr Eleazar Lòpez Hernández, an expert in indigenous theology, and a member of the Zapoteca people in Mexico, confirmed that the Churches of Latin America need to express their faith according to their traditions. This is what the proposal for an Amazonian rite is based on, he said. We need to generate something that is “in tune with local traditions”, added Fr Hernández. “Our people have their own religious experiences that give meaning to their lives”. We cannot focus on only one culture or follow a single pathway, he explained.

Sr Mariluce dos Santos Mesquita held that the indigenous people, are here “to say we have our own spirituality”. “We already celebrate rites and live with our cultural values and traditions”, she said. “We are the result of evangelization but we interact and live our celebrations bringing our symbols and Jesus’ message”, said Sister Mariluce. “We need to delve deeper into our spirituality and the Word of God”, through sharing, fraternity, and gestures of solidarity, she said.

A prominent member of the Ashaninca indigenous people in Peru, Mr Delio Siticonatzi Camaiteri, held that the indigenous people of the Amazon Region have their own “world view”,

which encompasses nature, and which “brings us closer to God”. As indigenous people, “we experience harmony with all living beings”, he said. “We have our own rituals but they are centered on Jesus Christ. There is nothing else”, he asserted. Realising “the importance of defending the earth where we live,” he opined that the Synod experience is a source of hope for indigenous people that has allowed them to speak up for their rights.

Father Peter Hughes has closely been engaged in the formation and in the development of the REPAM - the Church network for the defense of Amazonia. He noted the indigenous people of the Amazon “have become the subjects of their own history, and they want a place at the table. They demand to be heard at the concert of nations.”

At the synod, “the periphery speaks from the center with the awareness that its experience is heard as a prophetic voice for the whole church,” said Antonio Spadaro, S.J., a synod member and the editor in chief of *La Civiltà Cattolica*.

The Asian Situation

It may be noted that there are approximately 370 million Indigenous people in the world, belonging to 5,000 different groups, in 90 countries worldwide. Indigenous people live in every region of the world, but about 70% of them live in Asia. Coming to India we have 104 million indigenous peoples constituting 8.6% of the national population. Although there are 705 officially recognized ethnic groups, there are many more ethnic groups that would qualify for the scheduled tribe status, but which are not officially recognized. The tribal population in India covers approximately 15% of the country and the majority is found in central India.

By taking away forest lands for industries and plantation forestry instead of preserving natural species that provide

livelihood to these people, the government was depriving them of the basic means of livelihood.

Response of the Indian Church

Listening to the various interventions of the Synod so far, Cardinal Gracias says he feels the Church is really one body. He told *Malaysian Herald* that Asia, as well as India, have challenges that are similar to the people of Amazonia.

The cardinal learnt a lot about the challenges of the people of the Amazon which are a little different but essentially the same, such as making the Gospel values present and reaching out to the poor in the peripheries.

Passion for the people: Another aspect of the Synod that struck the cardinal is the passionate care of the bishops of the Amazonia for their poor people who are suffering. The bishops are the voice of the voiceless. They are listening to the cry of the people against violence, exploitation, injustice and are passionately concerned about their future. Hence, being in the Synod has been a good learning experience and inspiration for Cardinal Gracias.

Exploitation of the indigenous people: What came out strongly in the interventions, according to Cardinal Gracias, is the exploitation of the indigenous people. He says this is also happening in India.

“The Adivasis and the tribals are our indigenous people. Their land is being taken away. Legislation is being passed that deprive them of the privileges they have.”

The 74-year old cardinal explained that many of these original residents do not have proper documents. They are not accustomed to all this but they have been living in their lands for centuries. “All of a sudden, someone comes telling them they don’t have proper papers, so their land is being taken

away.”

Deforestation: Cardinal Gracias pointed out that India also has the problem of deforestation but to a lesser extent than in the Amazonia, where it is rampant. In India, corporate companies are taking over the land. He lamented that the green cover of the country is gradually diminishing. “Fortunately, the government has been speaking about the necessity for taking care of the climate” but in reality, the corporates” have been doing otherwise.

On the whole the response of the Indian Church has been lukewarm. Speaking to the students of Papal Seminary, Pune, Dr Binoy Jacob, Director, Loyola Institute of Peace Initiatives, Kochi, urged the Indian Church to learn from the Synod “to respect fellow human beings, respect the earth based on a living spirituality.”

“The Indian church did not even see that something is happening and the Synod is really significant to us,” said Fr Joby Tharamangalam, research scholar at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth.

Call for Conversion

By focusing narrowly on married deacons and Pachamama statue, we are forgetting the great spiritual insights for contemporary world. *The America Magazine* points out that “The synod was prophetic in placing Amazonian and indigenous communities at the center of the synod process and for making a clear option for these communities over foreign economic interests.” It adds: “At the heart of the synod process and the final document is conversion at the pastoral, cultural, ecological and synodal levels.”

On the last day of the Synod, the Holy Father warned against building walls and ignoring the traditions of those often on the

margins of society. His challenge to us calls for our own conversion. “How many times do those who are prominent, like the Pharisee with respect to the tax collector, raise up walls to increase distances, making other people feel even more rejected,” he asked. “Or by considering them backward and of little worth, they despise their traditions, erase their history, occupy their lands, and usurp their goods.”

Cry of the Poor

Pope Francis emphasised that “the best prayer is that of gratitude, that of praise.” Such prayers, says Sirach, “will reach to the clouds” (35:21). While the prayer of those who presume that they are righteous remains earthly, crushed by the gravitational force of egoism, that of the poor person rises directly to God. The sense of faith of the People of God has seen in the poor “the gatekeepers of heaven”: The poor are the ones who will open wide or not the gates of eternal life. They were not considered bosses in this life, they did not put themselves ahead of others; they had their wealth in God alone. These persons are living icons of Christian prophecy.

In this Synod we have had the grace of listening to the voices of the poor and reflecting on the precariousness of their lives, threatened by predatory models of development. Yet precisely in this situation, many have testified to us that it is possible to look at reality in a different way, accepting it with open arms as a gift, treating the created world not as a resource to be exploited but as a home to be preserved, with trust in God. He is our Father and, Sirach says again, “he hears the prayer of one who is wronged” (v. 16). How many times, even in the Church, have the voices of the poor not been heard and perhaps scoffed at or silenced because they are inconvenient. Let us pray for the grace to be able to listen to the cry of the poor: this is *the cry of hope* of the Church. The cry of the poor is the

Church's cry of hope. When we make their cry our own, we can be certain, our prayer too will reach to the clouds.

Reaching out to Asia through “Asian Francis”

Pope Francis's choice Sunday, December 8, 2019, about a month after the end of the Amazon Synod, to name the 62-year-old Cardinal Luis Antonio Tagle of Manila in the Philippines the new prefect of the Congregation for the Evangelization of Peoples is very significant, notes Raymond J de Souza writing in *The National Catholic Registrar*.

Tagle replaces the 73-year-old Italian Cardinal Fernando Filoni, the Vatican's former ambassador in Iraq who refused to vacate Baghdad in 2003 when American bombs began to fall, and who now moves on to become the grand master of the Equestrian Order of the Holy Sepulchre of Jerusalem.

His appointment bolsters the ranks of Vatican personnel on board with the pope's agenda, thereby giving Francis more leverage to get things done inside his own shop.

Tagle is widely known as the “Asian Francis,” as Cardinal Tagle is often called,” a social justice-oriented moderate who's known best for his advocacy for immigrants and the poor, and whose personal lifestyle speaks to modesty and simplicity. As a young bishop, he was known for bicycling to cover Mass assignments by himself and for inviting local beggars into his residence for lunch.

Tagle's theological background reflects the progressive, reform-oriented wing of the Second Vatican Council. He served as a member of the editorial board of the multi-volume *History of Vatican II* edited by Giuseppe Alberigo

and Alberto Melone, key figures in the “Bologna School” embodying the liberal reading of the council.

Again, the Congregation for the Evangelization of Peoples is a big deal on the Vatican scene, and it’s about to become bigger.

Traditionally known by its old Latin name *Propaganda Fidei*, the department is responsible for the Church in mission territories, which has traditionally made it both politically and financially powerful in Rome and around the world.

Today, under the terms of the pope’s impending overhaul of Vatican structures, it’s set to become the centerpiece of a new mega-Dicastery for Evangelization, taking over the Pontifical Council for the New Evangelization as well. The idea is that this new department for evangelization will become number one in the Vatican’s internal pecking order, supplanting the Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith, traditionally known as *La Suprema*, or “the supreme.”

Moreover, the mere fact that Tagle’s in charge also boosts *Propaganda Fidei*’s profile, given that he’s a celebrity in his own right with a large and devoted following on the Catholic lecture circuit. He’s a gifted communicator who wears his heart on his sleeve, and he’s capable of doing it successfully in multiple languages.

Further, Tagle’s appointment also puts an exclamation point on the “Philippines’ moment” in global Catholicism. Today, the Philippines are the third largest Catholic country in the world, with a Catholic population of around 90 million, sitting behind only Brazil and Mexico and comfortably in front of the United States. Compared to Brazil and Mexico, however, Catholicism in the Philippines tends to be more dynamic, with higher average

levels of faith and practice and a larger crop of vocations to the priesthood and religious life.

In many spots on the Catholic map, including parts of the U.S., Filipinos today are the new Irish, meaning the missionaries who keep local churches alive. Filipino expats are also the backbone of local Catholic churches in a staggering variety of settings, from Saudi Arabia, where they work in the oil industry and as domestic servants to wealthy Saudi families, to Australia and even Tagle's new home in Italy.

Finally, putting Tagle into such a meaningful post on the Roman stage cements his status as a possible successor to Francis. Assuming a conclave isn't on the horizon for a while, the timing likely would put Tagle into his mid-to-late 60s, which might strike electors as about right - young enough to govern, but old enough not to be there forever. Certainly, Francis enthusiasts would see a lot to like in the charismatic Filipino "bishop of the poor." Can we visualise an Asian Bishop who speaks for the poor!

Let us hope and pray that the Asian Church will learn these lessons of synodality, ecological conversion, respecting the earth and the indigenous mentality and listening to the cry of the poor!